

in Hunan. In 1983, hybrid varieties HA79317-7 and Xiangwanxian-1 which have moderate resistance to BPH, were grown in about 6% of the hybrid rice area (36% of the Hunan rice area). One of HA79317-7's parents is IR36;

Xiangwanxian-1 is a cross with ASD7 (both IR36 and ASD7 carry gene *bph 2*). Most hybrid rice varieties appeared to be moderately resistant in the field. Most local improved varieties were susceptible to BPH. This

investigation suggests that HA79317-7 and Xiangwanxian-1 and the hybrid combinations currently used, that are not known to have resistance genes, have not caused the phenotypic changes in *N. lugens* populations of Hunan. □

A parasitic nematode in white striated planthopper (WSPH) of rice

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The occurrence of parasitic nematodes in some leafhoppers and planthoppers of rice has been reported in many places. *Nephotettix* spp., *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) were reported to have been parasitized by two parasitic nematodes — *Agamermis unka* and *Hexamermis* sp.

We have encountered some individuals of WSPH *Nisia nervosa* (Motsch), another planthopper occasionally seen on rice, parasitized by an unclassified nematode (see figure). The nematode measures about 2-3.5 cm long. About 12% of field-collected WSPH were observed to be parasitized during the winter months (Nov-Dec) at Annamalainagar.

Nisia nervosa adult parasitized by nematode.

A new rice leaffolder (LF) in Kerala

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LF infestation in Kerala has so far been attributed mainly to a single species, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. But recent reports from other states indicate that the LF population is a multispecies complex. Observation of LF-damaged leaves in ricefields in and around RARS revealed a new species, *Brachmia atrotraea* Meyrick (family Gelechiidae), which was earlier reported in Cuttack, Orissa, and Madurai, Tamil Nadu, and in Malaysia. The population is commonly found in leaves of ratoon rice and in weeds.

The fully grown larva is distinguished from other LF in having a distinct black head and a prothoracic shield. It folds rice leaves longitudinally, mostly from the tip, and feeds by scraping the epidermal tissues (Fig. 1). Larval length is about 9 mm.

1. Larva of *Brachmia atrotraea* with its leaf fold. Kerala, India, 1987.

2. Pupa of *B. atrotraea*.

3. Adult of *B. atrotraea*.

The brownish larva, measuring about 6 mm, pupates in the folded leaf (Fig. 2). The pale strawcolored and small adult emerges within 1 wk (Fig. 3). Probably because its damage is similar to that caused by *C. medinalis*, *B. atrotraea* went unnoticed. □